

MANIFESTATION OF DESTRUCTIVE RELIGIOUS BEHAVIOR IN PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract. *In three articles, the manifestation of destructive religious behavior in connection with the characteristics of a person was studied on the basis of research. The connection of this situation with the socio-psychological environment is explained on the basis of theories.*

Key words: *destructive religious behavior, religious fanaticism, sect, "psychological immunity", physical aggression, frustration, negativism.*

ПРОЯВЛЕНИЕ ДЕСТРУКТИВНОГО РЕЛИГИОЗНОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ В ЛИЧНОСТНЫХ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКАХ

Аннотация. *В трех статьях на основе исследований изучалось проявление деструктивного религиозного поведения в связи с особенностями личности. Связь этой ситуации с социально-психологической средой объясняется на основе теорий.*

Ключевые слова: *деструктивное религиозное поведение, религиозный фанатизм, секта, "психологический иммунитет", физическая агрессия, фрустрация, негативизм.*

Every day, the changes that take away energy in all aspects of human life are redeeming themselves in different ways of looking at the psyche of each individual. At this point, until today, the phenomenon of destructive religious behavior occupies a separate place in the life of society and the state. Religious destructive actions - deviant personal behavior is calculated in order to self-regulate or conform to the letter, related to receiving benefits from something or people. As a rule, such behavior is determined by the search for the meaning of life, which is a natural state, the feeling of stress and insecurity caused by personal problems of social needs, burden, fear, anxiety. Recently, interest in religion has increased dramatically in our society. Because of this, the weather in the people is dry, fear, and as a result stress has increased. In such conditions, interest in the problem of life and death, not getting sick, is intensified. It includes spiritual, moral and people. In this situation, religion - a measure of continuous fear and oppression of humanity - has become invisible in quality. Again, it serves as a psychological motivation to get out of a tense situation.

K. Jung believes that religious life has a general semantic structure, without which life would be meaningless for people, and it allows you to establish connections with the most images (archetypes) of your collective unconscious. It should be noted that religious destructive behavior is one of the forms of drug addiction (smoking, drug addiction, etc.), eating disorder (overeating, starvation, food refusal), gambling (gambling addiction) and addictive behavior, according to , destructive religious behavior is manifested in two forms:

1. Religious fanaticism;

2. Joining a Sect.

Religious fanaticism is characterized by zeal for a specific type of religious activity, inconsiderate persecution of like-minded people, and a lack of ability to analyze one's own behavior. The following categories of people are most likely to experience religious fanaticism:

- is not capable of critical thinking that controls emotions in their actions;
- characterized by easy offer;
- easily responds to someone's influence;
- those who do not have a formed worldview and system of value orientations.

Religious fanaticism has very serious consequences not only for the individual, but also for the entire society. Attraction to a sect is a psychological processing of a person's mind, all of its techniques are well known to advertising specialists, employees of relevant agencies and, of course, leaders of sectarian organizations. But the common man knows nothing of the methods designed to enslave his mind, and therefore he is defenseless. Scam new members: Recruiters who harass people on the street almost never reveal the true name of their organization. Experts know that it is impossible to break a person's natural psychological defenses with simple trust. Therefore, in order to control a person, it is necessary to penetrate into his inner world. Psychological methods are usually used for this.

Thus, religiously destructive behavior is a painful process within religious denominations that manifests itself in religious fanaticism, religious extremism, and religious crime. The most effective forms and methods of preventing the involvement of young people in destructive currents are: interactive forms of work; individual; a vivid example from the life of former supporters; lectures; seminars; learning by doing, etc.

It is known from the science of psychology that when a person interacts with the social environment, that is, when he goes through the process of socialization, he decides as a "Person". Of course, today's conditions demand this from humanity. Advances in science and technology and the use of social networks are increasing not only among young people, but also among adults. While this situation serves as a means of independent and individual learning of some young people and achieving great achievements, unfortunately, this situation causes the formation of destructive religious behavior in some young people. Following informal social networks, continuously playing games that have a very negative effect on the human psyche and cause neurosis, addiction and brutality are the reasons for this. The brutal murder of a 19-year-old boy at a school in Kazan, Russia shocked the whole world. Killing 9 people and injuring 32 people by the young man shows his destructive religious behavior. His self-declaration as God, preparation for this crime for two years, unwillingness to recognize his parents, strong hatred towards people, aggression and neurosis are the sad results of this situation. Here Leonardo da Vinci's words "It is easier to resist at the beginning than at the end" are relevant. That is, preventing the formation of destructive religious behavior among young people begins with creating a healthy psychological environment in the family.

Psychoprophylactic measures aimed at preventing destructive religious behavior among young people include:

1. First of all, create a healthy psychological environment in the family;
2. Treating the child as a separate person from a young age;

3. Together with secular, modern education, religious education - teaching the fundamentals of each religion, forming a correct and reasonable religious outlook;

4. Early prevention and elimination of self-doubt and stress in young people, which is the main "hook" of various alien sects;

5. Satisfying the need of "Social belonging and recognition" according to A. Maslau's hierarchy in young people.

According to American social psychologist D. Maers, middle class youth are the most vulnerable, because they are easier, more susceptible to social influence, unlike upper class youth. To sum up, today's demand is to create a strong "psychological immunity" against foreign elements in the individual, along with living in harmony with the times.

Based on the above theories, we conducted research on 150 teenagers who believe in Islam and Christianity. In order to achieve the goal of this research, the questionnaire, Shmishek's "Character Accentuation" questionnaire, V.V. Stolin and S.R. Panteleev's "Attitude towards oneself", Bassa-Darki's Aggressiveness Study Questionnaire, O.D. Smirnov "Measuring religious activity" methodology was used. Also, statistical methods based on Spss-14 program (Student-T, Mann-Whitney, Kruskal-Wallis, Sperman) in psychological processing of research results, comparison of gender, group and age differences and study of mutual dependence-correlation. was also used. Below are some of the results of our research.

Analysis of research results according to the Kruskal-Wallis criterion (for non-parametric data) (n=150).

1-Table

Scales	Character type	N	Mean Rank	H	p
Asthenic	Official	27	29,91	0,348	0,022
	Excitable	9	31,14		
	Emotive	25	33,89		
	Total	61			
Stenic	Official	27	28,67	2,926	0,015
	Excitable	9	40,17		
	Emotive	25	30,22		
	Total	61			
Physical agresian	Official	27	26,39	3,165	0,003
	Excitable	9	35,39		
	Emotive	25	27,92		
	Total	61			
Negativism	Official	27	29,56	0,383	0.251
	Excitable	9	33,11		
	Emotive	25	31,80		
	Total	61			
The crown	Official	27	29,83	0,218	0,012
	Excitable	9	31,83		

	Emotive	25	31,96		
	Total	61			
Guilt	Official	27	27,57	3,350	0,006
	Excitable	9	27,78		
	Emotive	25	35,86		
	Total	61			

Explanation: $p \leq 0,05$ (95 %)*, $p \leq 0,01$ (99%)**, $p \leq 0,001$ (99.9%***).

According to this table, a difference was observed in the Asthenic scale with a 95% confidence level ($H=0.348$; $p \leq 0.05$). That is, people with an emotional character type have asthenic characteristics compared to people with an excitable and formal character type: talking about deep and diverse feelings towards God, feelings of helplessness, imperfection, and pain in front of God. it is higher.

A difference with a 95% confidence level was observed in the stenic scale ($H=2.926$; $p \leq 0.05$). That is, people with an excitable character type have higher characteristics of Stenicity than people with an emotive and formal character type: feelings of power, pleasure, and inspiration in relation to the divine.

A difference with a 99% confidence level was observed in the scale of physical aggression ($H=3.165$; $p \leq 0.01$). That is, people with an excitable character type have higher cases of physical aggressiveness, i.e. use of force and violence against others, compared to people with an emotional and formal character type.

A difference with a 95% confidence level was observed in the anxiety scale ($H=0.218$; $p \leq 0.05$). That is, people with an emotional character type have higher cases of depression than people with an excitable and formal character type.

A difference was observed in the guilt scale with a 99% confidence level ($H=3.350$; $p \leq 0.01$). That is, people with an emotional character type have a higher level of feeling guilty about events and people than people with an excitable and formal character type.

In short, destructive religious behavior is directly related to individual psychological characteristics of a person. Therefore, it is important to develop a program of psychoprophylactic measures aimed at preventing this condition in individuals and to put it into practice.

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